

D5.6 First CDE Report

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1.0	27.03.2024	Final version	Paavo Antikainen (KASKAS)

Deliverable Information

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Instrument	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach
Dx.x	Deliverable number
PMG	Project Management Group
PC	Project Coordinator
ICEBERG	Innovative Community Engagement for Building Effective Resilience and Arctic-Ocean Pollution-Control Governance in the context of Climate Change

1 Introduction

This deliverable describes the very first communication, dissemination, exploitation and outreach activities done during the first three months of the project. The production of the first deliverables and building the communication infrastructure of the project have defined the dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach activities of the three first months. A brief overview of the actions implemented at the very beginning of the project can be found in the table below.

Table 1. DECO actions implemented at the very beginning of the project

Category	M1-M3
Infrastructure and Collaboration	Establishing DECO Board M1 DECO Strategy (including two co-creation workshops with DECO Board) M3 Project's visual identity M3
Materials for the consortium	Preliminary PPT template for the kick off
Website and social media	Facebook page and first posts M1 One pager website M1 Website M3

2 Visual identity

The visual identity was among the initial tasks carried out for the project at the very early stage. The visual identity was designed by KASKAS in collaboration with the Project Coordinator. It includes the project's logo and visual elements such as a colour palette, fonts and photography style.

A more comprehensive and detailed description and instructions for applying the visual identity can be found in D5.1 and ICEBERG's upcoming brand book.

3 Website

The project website (D5.1) was published in M3. Before the final project website is published, a temporary one-pager has been used to provide the basic information about the project, from the end of M1 onwards. The website URL is <https://arcticeberg.eu>.

ICEBERG project's website will be updated regularly and developed further as needed. The website is maintained and updated by KASKAS, but all the project partners contribute by producing content and suggesting options to the website.

See D5.1 for further information.

4 DECO strategy

Dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach (DECO) activities are crucial to increase the societal impact of the project. The DECO strategy (D5.2) describes the approach for communicating project progress, disseminating results and facilitating their availability for exploitation. Its goal is to ensure effective planning, management and implementation of DECO activities.

Production of the DECO strategy was led by KASKAS in close collaboration with the entire ICEBERG consortium. A survey to the consortium was conducted in January 2024, marking the beginning of the strategy process. The process continued with two co-creation workshops with DECO Board members, both held in February 2024, where different sections of the strategy were further developed. The DECO strategy was finalized in M3.

See D5.2 for further information.

5 DECO Board

The DECO Board's key objective is to design, tailor, localize, test and execute DECO activities related to the project. The DECO Board was established (T5.3.1) in M1 and it consists of one representative per work package and per case study as well as the Scientific Coordinator (see table 2). The Board meets regularly to ensure smooth communication within the project.

During M2-M3 the DECO board was closely involved in the DECO strategy process by participating in strategy workshops and commenting on the strategy draft before it was finalized. The DECO board will focus on its actual tasks from M4 onwards.

Table 2. The Composition of the DECO Board

WP/Case Study	Names of Representatives/Affiliation	Email
WP1	Markus Schartau / GEOMAR	mschartau@geomar.de
WP2	Apostolos Papakonstantinou / SCI <i>Gaud Dervilly / ONIRIS (Substitute)</i>	apapak@scidrones.com <i>gaud.dervilly@inrae.fr</i>
WP3	Adam Stepien / ULAP <i>Jóse Luiz Moutinho / AIRCentre (Substitute)</i> <i>Valerie de Liedekerke / AIRCentre (Substitute)</i>	adam.stepien@ulapland.fi <i>jose.moutinho@aircentre.org</i> <i>valerie.deliedekerke@aircentre.org</i>
WP4	Anne Chahine / GFZ (RIFS) <i>Christine Liang / UFZ (Substitute)</i>	anne.chahine@rifs-potsdam.de <i>christine.liang@ufz.de</i>
WP5	Paavo Antikainen / KASKAS <i>KASKAS Team (Substitute)</i>	paavo.antikainen@kaskas.fi <i>iceberg-wp5@lists.oulu.fi</i>
WP6	Élise Lépy / UOULU	elise.lepy@oulu.fi
Svalbard	Beatrice Rosso / CNR	beatrice.rosso@isp.cnr.it
Greenland (Kalaallit Nunaat)	Ilona Mettiäinen / ULAP	ilona.mettiainen@ulapland.fi
Iceland	Joan Nymand Larsen / SAI	jnl@unak.is
Scientific Coordinator	Thora Herrmann / UOULU	thora.herrmann@oulu.fi

6 A platform for citizen participation

The development process of the citizen participation platform (T5.3.3) is in progress with WP2 (UOULU, UFZ, KASKAS) and WP4. An open-source and free interactive mapping platform, such as *uMap* (which uses OpenStreetMap layers and can be embed in a website) or *Mapbox* (also OpenStreetMap-based) will be used as a data visualisation and analysis platform for citizen participation in the ICEBERG project. The interactive mapping platform will be linked on the project website. The platform serves as a primary tool for mapping locally observed changes and reported data, emphasizing the categorization and labeling of litter depicted in photos along with short descriptions. Additionally, it records observed changes in both marine and terrestrial environments attributed to pollution and climate change-induced stressors, such as shifts in fauna, vegetation, and beach dynamics, and impacts on land-and sea-based activities, all facilitated by citizen observation and engagement. The map would display different regions of the study sites and each geotagged point on the map would represent one report, with the option to click the point and further expand the reported data along with the uploaded photo, or video or audiofile. The development of the interactive map is currently ongoing.

See D5.2 for further information.

7 Conclusions

Production of the first deliverables and building the communication infrastructure of the project has defined the CDE activities of the three first months. In the coming months, the project's communication activities will focus on promoting the project via the project's communication channels (website & social media), producing more material for the project and establishing connections with sibling projects and other networks (See D5.2 for further information).